

Enlivening Performance Art: Enhanced Interactivity through Embodied Cognition and Real-Time Physical Visualization on Swarm Tangible Interfaces

Yue Zhu
China Academy of Art
yukizhuyue@outlook.com

Zhiyuan Zhou
China Academy of Art
3210601057@caa.edu.cn

Fenggui Rao
China Academy of Art
admin@whitesir.cn

ABSTRACT

This project explores the use of tangible interfaces in the art of live performance by combining embodied cognition and real-time mapping techniques, aiming to broaden the boundaries of performance through digital physicalization methods. We have modified MIT’s open source Rovable robotics to be able to flexibly climb on soft three-dimensional surfaces, enhancing the creativity of both performers and audiences through this tangible interface. In addition, this study introduces techniques that combine OpenCV ArUco marker recognition and real-time mapping to broaden the possibilities of live performance in several ways, including influencing the performance and real-time AIGC visualization effects through interactions and experimenting with different visualization algorithms to enrich the content of live performances.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and significance of human-robot collaborative performance

Live coding engages dynamically with various creative practices such as choreography, visual arts, poetry, and especially music, nurturing new forms of expression. This particularly emphasizes improvisational composition within a broad spectrum of performance art (“Live Coding: A User’s Manual” n.d.). Simultaneously, the field of robotic art is thriving—as evidenced by its prominent presence in contemporary art scenes (Herath, Kroos, and Stelarc 2016; “Robots & Art – Exploring an Unlikely Symbiosis” n.d.; “Ars Electronica” n.d.). The etymological roots of robots trace back to theatre, illustrating a deep-seated connection with artistic expression (Herath, Kroos, and Stelarc 2016). At the confluence of live coding and robotic art, innovative projects have surfaced that focus on human-robot collaborative performances. For instance, “BOX – GMUNK” (n.d.) showcases the collaboration between humans and robotic arms to craft illusionary stage performances, while “Threading Space” (2023) delves into altering human spatial perception through the control of mobile robot swarms. Similar endeavors are increasingly featured at art festivals (“Ars Electronica” n.d.; “ArtBots: The Robot Talent Show” n.d.) and discussed in conferences (“Robots & Art – Exploring an Unlikely Symbiosis” n.d.), signaling a growing interest in this interdisciplinary field.

1.2 Research motivation

However, there remains a significant gap in achieving optimal joint action performance (“Joint Action: Bodies and Minds Moving Together” 2006), which, from the perspective of embodied cognition, can be seen as a deficit in the active, responsive process between a perceiving agent and its environment, influenced by the agent’s experiences, intentions, and bodily states. This gap underscores the challenge in real-time performance settings where humans and robots struggle to fully comprehend each other’s intentions, often resorting to pre-rehearsed sequences rather than truly improvisational interactions. While live coding and improvisational composition have been shown to enhance creativity and offer fresh insights for human performers, we believe these benefits can extend to human-robot collaborative performances, suggesting a rich area for exploration. Therefore, our research is driven by the desire to bridge this gap, aiming to enhance joint action in human-robot collaborative performances, particularly through improvisation, to foster more dynamic and intuitively synchronized interactions.

1.3 Potential of TUIs and physical visualization in improvising performances

According to the interaction model of Tangible User Interfaces (TUI) outlined by Ullmer and Ishii (2000), TUIs stand out from Graphic User Interfaces (GUIs) due to their integration of physical and digital representations—for instance, tangible objects that can be manipulated spatially versus digital graphics and audio. This integration enables TUIs to significantly reduce learning costs for users by streamlining the transition from digital information to user interaction. By providing physical representations that are directly linked to their digital counterparts, TUIs facilitate a more intuitive understanding of the system, particularly beneficial in improvisational performance contexts (Ullmer and Ishii 2000).

1.4 List of contributions

- Expansion of Rovable’s (Dementyev et al. 2016) capabilities for spatial performance, enhancing its interactivity in dynamic settings with customized modules for improvising live performance.
- Introduction of a real-time physical visualization method through TUI-based tracking and mapping, enhancing visibility and interpretability of data in human-robot collaborative performance.
- Simplification of hardware deployment to lower technical barriers for artists, making the system more accessible.
- Incorporation of creative algorithms to diversify visual effects, expanding artistic expression in performances.

2 Related work

The concept and design of our work are built upon previous work on TUIs for ubiquitous computing, human-robot collaborative performance, real-time projection mapping and physical visualization.

2.1 TUIs for ubiquitous computing

Ubiquitous computing has witnessed to develop with TUIs (Kang 2011), but not limited to. Live Wire by “Natalie Jeremienko: Live Wire – ACM SIGGRAPH ART SHOW ARCHIVES” (n.d.) is one of the earliest examples of visualizing digital information in a tangible representation (kc7txm 2017) which ideally couples to the identity and physical configuration of representational artifacts and makes the system easier to understand (Ullmer and Ishii 2000). Later examples like “HERMITS” (n.d.) explore a modular system for table-top, wheeled robots offering a variety of interactive functionality, one the applications of which is to serve as storytelling systems on tables. Yu et al. (2023) uses rigging swarm robots on ceilings for spatial interaction as actuated TUIs and Dementyev et al. (2016) proposes an interaction space for mobile on-body TUIs to develop application scenarios including on-body sensing, modular display, tactile feedback, and interactive clothing. Those actuated TUIs in everyday space have depicted a scenario of ubiquitous computing where the space has gradually merged into a whole. However the trend, these TUIs are still scattered around the space. Is it possible to have a form link those slices of space together? Based on this imagination, we extend the flexible surface climbing capacity to a larger space and further the spatial performance stage.

2.2 Human-robot collaborative performance

As previously mentioned in introduction section, the fusion of live coding and robotic art has given rise to various projects that focus on human-robot collaborative performances. For instance, “BOX – GMUNK” (n.d.) showcases a collaboration between human and robotic arms to produce an illusionary stage performance, and they customized a software called BD Movie for motion-capturing the view of an actual person watching the performance and then applied this natural movement to a camera path which can be reckoned as an attempt for computer to understand human’s intentions and bridge the gap in human-robot collaborative performance, boosting joint action performance (“Joint Action: Bodies and Minds Moving Together” 2006). “Threading Space” (2023) investigates the alteration of human spatial perception through the control of a robot swarm, whereas it’s more like pre-arranged rather than improvising performance. We drew inspiration from existing human-robot collaborative performances but innovated by employing digital physicalization to enhance interpretability between robots and spatial data and supporting constrained improvisation with preset sensor-responsive outputs, which doesn’t require complex and costly computational electrical systems.

Figure 1: Scenario of TUIs linked spatial live performance and the way human and robot collaborate for improvisation.

2.3 Real-time projection mapping and data physical visualization

The method of real-time projection mapping is widely used for the application of data physical visualization (“Tangible CityScape” n.d.; “Radical Atoms: Beyond Tangible Bits, Toward Transformable Materials: Interactions: Vol 19, No 1” n.d.; Li, Suzuki, and Nakagaki 2023; “Secure and Secret Cooperation in Robot Swarms | Science Robotics” n.d.), which has emerged from digital fabrication, actuated tangible interfaces, and shape-changing displays (Jansen et al. 2015). “Tangible CityScape” (n.d.) and Li, Suzuki, and Nakagaki (2023) show the potential application in dynamic geographic planning and “Overview < Tangible Swarm: See the Unseen – MIT Media Lab” (n.d.) is developed as a toolkit for visualizing the complicated in robot systems. We further develop the application scenario of “Overview < Tangible Swarm: See the Unseen – MIT Media Lab” (n.d.) in live performance.

3 Design and implementation of interactive improvising performance framework

In this section, we outline the overall design space and implementation of our proof-of-concept prototype of this interactive framework for improvising human-robot collaborative live performance.

3.1 Scenario of TUIs linked spatial live performance

As discussed before, there is a trend for TUIs in everyday space to emerge into an integrity, thus we adapt Rovable (Dementyev et al. 2016), which has the ability of flexible clothing surface climbing with magnetic wheels, as a connection to link the slices of space and explore the application in live spatial performances as is depicted in Figure 1.

3.2 Adaptation and application of rovable for space-linking scenario

The ‘rovable’ units have been structurally and circuit-wise adapted to enable vertical navigation on fabric surfaces, an advancement that significantly diversifies the application scope within interactive performance art. We replace the initial customized PCB board with ESP32C3, leveraging its WiFi capability to control motors and wheels, and adapt the circuit design as is shown in Figure 2.b, accordingly, the structure design is also modified which aligns with adaptation of inner components. And We tested wheels with different 3D structures and found that the tread pattern affects the robot’s gripping force. The more tread fold inflection points there are, the stronger the fabric adhesion ability (Figure 2.c). Then we extended the on-body climbing to spatial climbing and designed an installation for test and demonstration. This enhancement facilitates space-linking scenarios, allowing for the dynamic integration of these units in multi-dimensional

Figure 2: Structure and circuit design of rovable for space-linking scenario.

performance environments. Such cluster control is essential for executing intricate interactive installations that extend across various planes, including vertical and overhead spaces. However, its efficiency is temporarily limited, and we will optimize the cluster control module in future work. On the other hand, our deployment with ESP32C3 significantly lowers the threshold for learning and development for artists.

3.3 Overall system design based on rovable and real-time projection mapping

3.3.1 Physical visualization and creative visual pattern

In our framework, ArUco markers are employed for the precise positioning and attitude estimation of tangible user interfaces (TUIs) using the OpenCV library, a method underscored by its adaptability across varying environmental conditions. These markers are affixed to the TUIs via modular magnetic units, ensuring both ease of application and tracking stability. Complementing this setup, IP cameras are positioned to monitor TUIs, facilitating real-time data assimilation into our remote control system to collect and visualize spatial data and embodied data of TUIs effectively. Our approach integrates digital physicalization and stream diffusion techniques to dynamically convert data into visual formats (Figure 4.b), enhancing audience engagement through visual storytelling. We employ StreamDiffusion (Figure 4.b4) an opensource project, as discussed by Kodaira et al. (2023), to translate data into visual information using digital physicalization. This process is enhanced by the residual classifier-free guidance (RCFG) algorithm, facilitating rapid image style transfer based on spatial art data, thus enabling real-time interactive art mapping. To augment this, we integrate image digitization techniques from OpenProcessing, eg. the VaporMotion sketch (“VapoMotion - A5 - OpenProcessing” n.d.), broadening our visual repertoire and fostering innovative avenues for spatial interactive art. These methodologies collectively empower our system to produce dynamic, responsive visual content that significantly enhances the depth and engagement of our interactive installations.

4 Demonstration on Exhibition

Our interactive improvising performance framework was rigorously tested in a live exhibition setting, offering a unique opportunity to observe its real-world applicability and gather direct feedback from participants. The demonstration showcased the seamless integration of human performers and robots, highlighting the framework’s capability to facilitate an intuitive and collaborative artistic process.

During the exhibition, observers and participants experienced firsthand the dynamic interaction between the tangible interfaces and the robotic elements, providing valuable insights into the system’s responsiveness, user-friendliness, and artistic potential.

Figure 3: Interactive system overview and control architecture.

Figure 4: Mapping diagram and creative visual pattern.

Figure 5: *Demonstration on exhibition.*

5 Discussion and Future Design Space

The live exhibition provided critical feedback that has been instrumental in identifying the strengths and areas for improvement in our framework. Participants noted the innovative use of TUIs in enhancing the interactivity and expressiveness of the performance. However, challenges such as the need for faster real-time data processing and more robust robot autonomy were highlighted.

Future work will focus on addressing these challenges by optimizing the system’s computational efficiency and exploring more advanced algorithms for autonomous robotic behavior. Additionally, we aim to expand the design space by integrating more diverse sensors and interaction modalities, further blurring the lines between the physical and digital realms in performance art.

6 Conclusion

This paper proposed a scenario for swarm TUIs to augment the interactivity of live human-robot performance by real-time digital physicalization. We demonstrated this concept with a proof-of-concept implementation in a live exhibition. While the application of Rovable mitigate the spatial inconformity with the space-linking scenario, projection mapping for real-time data visualization of swarm robotics reduces temporal latency to certain degree. Meanwhile, our workflow of deployment and incorporation of diverse algorithmic visualization forms make the whole process more accessible and accountable for the artists community. We hope this paper provides some novel perspectives to enhance interactivity with the potential of integrating advanced technologies with cooperative creativity to push the boundaries of traditional performance art.

6.1 Acknowledgments

We appreciate Cun Lin and Rao Yin (from China Academy of Art) giving practical advice on the demonstration of live performance, which became the basis of exhibition implementation. We greatly thank Zhitao Yu from China Academy of Art for his assistant in welding a batch of modified rovable robotics according to our circuit design and building part of physical exhibition installation. We thank the Rovable research team from MIT and technical documentation which helped us to build the architecture introduced in this paper. Lastly, we thank China Academy of Art for providing us with a research and exhibition environment to conduct our work.

References

- 10 “Ars Electronica.” n.d. *Ars Electronica*. Accessed March 7, 2024. <https://ars.electronica.art/news/en/>.
- “ArtBots: The Robot Talent Show.” n.d. Accessed March 7, 2024. <https://artbots.org/previous.shtml>.
- “BOX – GMUNK.” n.d. Accessed March 7, 2024. <https://gmunk.com/BOX>.
- Dementyev, Artem, Hsin-Liu (Cindy) Kao, Inrak Choi, Deborah Ajilo, Maggie Xu, Joseph A. Paradiso, Chris Schmandt, and Sean Follmer. 2016. “Rovables: Miniature On-Body Robots as Mobile Wearables.” In *Proceedings of the 29th Annual Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology*, 111–20. UIST ’16. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2984511.2984531>.
- Herath, Damith, Christian Kroos, and Stelarc, eds. 2016. *Robots and Art*. Cognitive Science and Technology. Singapore: Springer Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-0321-9>.
- “HERMITS.” n.d. Accessed March 8, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3379337.3415831>.
- Jansen, Yvonne, Pierre Dragicevic, Petra Isenberg, Jason Alexander, Abhijit Karnik, Johan Kildal, Sriram Subramanian, and Kasper Hornbæk. 2015. “Opportunities and Challenges for Data Physicalization.” In *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 3227–36. Seoul Republic of Korea: ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2702123.2702180>.
- “Joint Action: Bodies and Minds Moving Together.” 2006. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences* 10 (2): 70–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2005.12.009>.
- Kang, Byeong. 2011. “Ubiquitous Computing Environment Threats and Defensive Measures.” *International Journal of Multimedia and Ubiquitous Engineering* 2 (June).
- kc7txm. 2017. “Designing Calm Technology.” *Computer Repair Blog*. <https://www.karlstechnology.com/blog/designing-calm-technology/>.
- Kodaira, Akio, Chenfeng Xu, Toshiki Hazama, Takanori Yoshimoto, Kohei Ohno, Shogo Mitsuohori, Soichi Sugano, Hanying Cho, Zhijian Liu, and Kurt Keutzer. 2023. “StreamDiffusion: A Pipeline-Level Solution for Real-Time Interactive Generation.” arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2312.12491>.
- Li, Jiatong, Ryo Suzuki, and Ken Nakagaki. 2023. “Physica: Interactive Tangible Physics Simulation Based on Tabletop Mobile Robots Towards Explorable Physics Education.” In *Proceedings of the 2023 ACM Designing Interactive Systems Conference*, 1485–99. DIS ’23. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3563657.3596037>.
- “Live Coding: A User’s Manual.” n.d. *Live Coding: A User’s Manual*. Accessed March 7, 2024. <https://livecodingbook.toplap.org/book/>.
- “Natalie Jeremijenko: Live Wire – ACM SIGGRAPH ART SHOW ARCHIVES.” n.d. Accessed March 8, 2024. <https://digitalartarchive.siggraph.org/artwork/natalie-jeremijenko-live-wire/>.
- “Overview < Tangible Swarm: See the Unseen – MIT Media Lab.” n.d. Accessed March 8, 2024. <https://www.media.mit.edu/projects/tangible-swarm/overview/>.
- “Radical Atoms: Beyond Tangible Bits, Toward Transformable Materials: Interactions: Vol 19, No 1.” n.d. Accessed March 8, 2024. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2065327.2065337>.
- “Robots & Art – Exploring an Unlikely Symbiosis.” n.d. Accessed March 7, 2024. <https://roboticart.org/>.
- “Secure and Secret Cooperation in Robot Swarms | Science Robotics.” n.d. Accessed March 8, 2024. <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/scirobotics.abf1538?ijkey=.aUwZmhyN7RDA&keytype=ref&siteid=robotics>.
- “Tangible CityScope.” n.d. Accessed March 8, 2024. <https://tangible.media.mit.edu/project/tangible-cityscope>.
- “Threading Space.” 2023. *Ars Electronica Festival 2023 - Who Owns the Truth?* <https://ars.electronica.art/who-owns-the-truth/en/threading-space/>.
- Ullmer, B., and H. Ishii. 2000. “Emerging Frameworks for Tangible User Interfaces.” *IBM Systems Journal* 39 (3.4): 915–31. <https://doi.org/10.1147/sj.393.0915>.
- “VapoMotion - A5 - OpenProcessing.” n.d. Accessed March 8, 2024. <https://openprocessing.org/sketch/474396/>.
- Yu, Lilith, Chenfeng Gao, David Wu, and Ken Nakagaki. 2023. “AeroRigUI: Actuated TUIs for Spatial Interaction Using Rigging Swarm Robots on Ceilings in Everyday Space.” In *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–18. CHI ’23. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3544548.3581437>.